

Electrochemical Behaviour of Natural Humic and Hymatomelanic Acids Isolated from Diverse Soil Types of India

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Humic and hymatomelanic acids isolated from five different soils of varying organic matter contents were subjected to electrometric titrations. The electrometric studies, namely, those of interaction of the different humus fractions with bases and neutral salts, are clearly indicative of the polyelectrolytic behaviour of these high molecular acidic components. The similarity of the behaviour of natural humic acids with hymatomelanic acids was clearly noticeable, suggesting the genetic similarity between them.

In recent years the greater part of the chemical studies of humus has been concerned with the humic acid fraction. The available evidence suggests that the humic acid fraction represents either a single chemical substance or a group of closely related substances. There are good reasons for believing that humic acid is primarily non-nitrogenous and that the presence of nitrogen in many preparations is due to secondary combination with amino acids or protein, with quinone groups in the main molecule. In the soil, humic acid normally occurs as a metallic humic acid complex, the metal varying with the soil itself.

The term 'hymatomelanic acid' was first introduced by Hoppe-Seylor¹ for the substances extracted by alcohol from 'raw' humic acid. Oden regarded it as a compound possessing a number of characteristics such as solubility in water, alcohol and alkali, carbon content (62%) and equivalent weight (250). A different point of view was expressed by Shmuk² who denied the separate existence of hymatomelanic acid regarding it as a mixture of resin type compounds.

This group of substances has attracted the attention of investigators during recent years. Kukhareno and Ekaterinina³ have demonstrated the similarity of humic acids and hymatomelanic acids from coal, as shown by their elementary composition and by the functional groups present such as methoxyl, carboxyl and hydroxyl. According to Kukhareno, hymatomelanic acid can be formed both by synthesis from the products of decomposition of organic residues and also during the oxidative-hydrolytic destruction of humus substances by oxygen and moisture. Consequently, it is considered that like humic acid hymatomelanic acid is heterogeneous and is not an independent group of humus substances but an alcohol-soluble fraction of humic acid.

Polyfunctional humic and hymatomelanic acids contain such functional sites as carboxyl, hydroxyl, enolic, primary amino and imino groups. Most probably the carboxylic groups are aromatic in nature and a part of this acidity may originate in the side chains of macromolecules. The relative proportions of various functional groups in these acids are generally dependent on the nature and type of the soil from which they have been isolated.

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1. Hoppe-Seylor, *Z. Physiol. Chem.*, 1889, **13**, 66.

2. A. A. Shmuk, *Byull. Pochvoveda*, 1930, (5-7).

3. T. A. Kukhareno and L. N. Ekaterinina, *Pochvovedenie*, 1960, **12**, 64.

At the present time sufficient data are not available to give evidence of differences in the nature of humic substances of different soils. The results of comparative studies of humic acids and fulvic acids from the major soil types of the USSR by Russian chemists⁴ have shown regular differences in their nature and properties. Electrochemical behaviour of natural fulvic acids isolated from different sources have recently been studied⁵. No detailed study of the electrochemical properties of humic and hymatomelanic acids isolated from the diverse soil types of India has been carried out. The present work aims at having a fuller information in this direction. Electrometric methods involving potentiometric and conductometric titrations are quite informative as regards the functional groups and their relative proportions in soil humic and hymatomelanic acids.

EXPERIMENTAL

For the present investigation, one sample of surface soil each from Palampur, Chinsura, Dehra Dun, Darjeeling and Jodhpur has been selected for the isolation of humic and hymatomelanic acids. The organic matter contents of these soils are 2.60, 0.67, 5.50, 2.90 and 0.26% respectively.

0.5 *N* sodium carbonate solution was used for the extraction of humus from soil. The supernatant was allowed to stand overnight and centrifuged. The precipitate of crude humic acid obtained by acidifying it with HCl to pH 2-3 was separated in the centrifuge. The precipitate was redissolved with dilute sodium carbonate solution, reprecipitated and separated as before. The crude humic acid was at first dialysed against distilled water and then electro-dialysed for nearly a week. The electro-dialysed material was almost dried over water bath and then subjected to soxhlet extraction with 95% alcohol till the alcohol became colourless. The alcohol insoluble fraction containing humic acid and the dried alcohol soluble fraction containing hymatomelanic acid was dissolved separately in alkali and precipitated with HCl at pH 2-3. The precipitated humic and hymatomelanic acids were purified by washing and dialysis.

Continuous conductometric titrations were carried out with caustic soda in a cell of comparatively low cell constant using a Leeds-Northrup conductivity bridge at $30^{\circ} \pm 0.1^{\circ}$.

The potentiometric titrations were done with the help of a Cambridge pH-meter at $30^{\circ} \pm 0.1^{\circ}$. The titrations were carried out continuously with caustic soda in absence and presence of 1.0 *M* NaCl.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It has been observed during fractionation of humus that the predominating fraction is humic acid and the amount of hymatomelanic acid fraction is usually very small in all the soils, being almost negligible in Chinsura and Jodhpur soils.

The conductometric titrations which enable the equivalent point to be determined with greater accuracy are discussed first, and the graphs are shown in Figs. 1(A), 1(B) and 1(C)*. The legends given there indicate the nature and source of the acids and the titrants. All the conductometric titration curves of humic and hymatomelanic acids having the

* In order to save space the other graphs are omitted.

4. M. M. Kononova, *Soil Organic Matter*, Pergamon Press, New York, 1966.

5. Chhabi Datta and S. K. Mukherjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **45**, 555.

FIG.1(A) ●● CONDUCTOMETRIC TITRATION IN WATER WITH 0.05N NaOH (CONDUCTIVITY-SCALE ON LEFT SIDE OF LEFT HAND ORDINATE)
 FIG.2(A) ○○ POTENTIOMETRIC TITRATION IN WATER WITH 0.05N NaOH (PH-SCALE)
 △△ POTENTIOMETRIC TITRATION IN WATER WITH 0.05N NaOH IN PRESENCE OF 1M NaCl (PH-SCALE)

FIG.1(B) ●● CONDUCTOMETRIC TITRATION IN WATER WITH 0.05N NaOH (CONDUCTIVITY SCALE ON LEFT SIDE OF LEFT HAND ORDINATE)
 FIG.2(B) ○○ POTENTIOMETRIC TITRATION IN WATER WITH 0.05N NaOH (PH-SCALE)
 △△ POTENTIOMETRIC TITRATION IN WATER WITH 0.05N NaOH IN PRESENCE OF 1M NaCl (PH-SCALE)

FIG 1(C) CONDUCTOMETRIC TITRATION IN WATER WITH 0.05N NaOH (CONDUCTIVITY-SCALE)

FIG 2(C) POTENTIOMETRIC TITRATION IN WATER WITH 0.05N NaOH (PH-SCALE)

general features of weak acids show a single break indicating a monobasic behaviour of the respective acids excepting that of Jodhpur humic acid which has a second break in the titration curve.

Under comparable concentrations (5 mg/20 ml) the initial conductances (Table I) of humic and hymatomelanic acids also vary. The initial conductance appears to be almost

TABLE I

Concentration : 5 mg/20 ml.

Substance	Conductometric B.E.C. in m.e./100 gm	Specific conductance at $\alpha = 0$ mho cm^{-1} $\times 10^5$	Specific conductance at $\alpha = \frac{1}{2}$ mho cm^{-1} $\times 10^5$
<i>Humic acid from</i>			
Palampur	690	2.0	16.2
Chinsura	683	1.2	24.6
Dehra Dun	670	2.9	18.0
Darjeeling	680	2.0	11.4
Jodhpur	665	1.65	23.6
<i>Hymatomelanic acid from</i>			
Palampur	675	3.0	16.2
Dehra Dun	640	1.0	9.8
Darjeeling	690	1.8	12.0

entirely due to the hydrogen counter ions produced by the dissociation of these acids. Van Dijk⁶ has reported conductometric titration curves of both natural and synthetic humic acids, which resemble those obtained in the present work.

All the conductometric titration curves of hymatomelanic and humic acids (excepting those of Chinsura and Darjeeling) show a drop in specific conductance at low values of α , usually at about 3 to 4 percent neutralisation. The minimum most probably represents the amount of free hydrogen ion neutralised. This belief is strengthened by comparing the observed pH with that calculated from the amount of alkali required to reach the first break.

The base exchange capacities of different humic and hymatomelanic acid lie in the range of 665 to 690 m.e. and 640 to 690 m.e. respectively, whereas for synthetic humic acid⁷ they are in the range of 225 to 820 m.e. The specific conductances at the equivalence points

FIG. 3 (A) HUMIC ACID FROM

- PALAMPUR
- CHINSURA
- △ DEHRA DUN
- DARJEELING
- ▲ JODHPUR

FIG. 3. (B) HUMIC ACID (IN PRESENCE OF 1M NaCl) FROM

- PALAMPUR
- CHINSURA
- △ DEHRA DUN
- DARJEELING
- ▲ JODHPUR

6. H. Van Dijk, *Sci. Proc. Royal Dublin Soc.*, 1960, 1, Series A, 163-176.
7. S. Sur and S. K. Mukherjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 46, 451.

of humic and hymatomelanic acids vary from 11.4 to $24.6 \times 10^{-5} \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 9.8 to $16.2 \times 10^{-5} \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 30° respectively, whereas the corresponding values for synthetic humic acids⁷ lie at a somewhat lower range, *viz.*, 5.27 to $8.99 \times 10^{-5} \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 30° .

In general, the location of end points is somewhat more difficult in the potentiometric curves than those in the conductometric curves. Therefore, to locate the inflexion points more accurately, differential curves (not shown) for each titration have been constructed separately. The potentiometric curves are shown in Figs. 2(A), 2(B) and 2(C). The total acidity values of humic and hymatomelanic acids by potentiometric method (Table II) are always found to be smaller than those determined conductometrically. The equivalent weights of humic and hymatomelanic acids apparently depend on the time of interactions of the acids with alkali.

TABLE II

Concentration : 5 mg/40 ml.

Substance	Potentiometric B.E.C. in m.e./100 mg.	pK_{av} (from the graph) at $\alpha = 0.5$	pK_{int}	
			in absence of NaCl	in presence of 1 M NaCl
<i>Humic acid from</i>				
Palampur	675	6.85	5.70	3.50
Chinsura	670	8.87	7.12	4.40
Dehra Dun	640	7.92	6.00	4.58
Darjeeling	665	7.80	6.50	4.20
Jodhpur	645	7.72	5.85	3.20
<i>Hymatomelanic acid from</i>				
Palampur	665	7.48	6.30	4.25
Dehra Dun	625	7.66	5.65	4.05
Darjeeling	660	7.45	5.40	3.66

The inflexions in the potentiometric titration curves in presence of 1M NaCl are somewhat more pronounced than in its absence. It may be guessed that in presence of NaCl some of the acid groups are exchanged by Na^+ liberating free H^+ ions which cause the observed pH drop and a change in the titration curve.

The apparent pK_{av} (≈ 6.8 to 8.9) values were determined from the pH titration curves at 50% neutralisation. The addition of salt lowers, as expected the pK_{av} values (Table II). The reported pK_{av} values in absence of electrolyte for synthetic humic acids⁷ are in the range from 6.0 to 6.60. The reported value of pK_{av} for Merck's humic acid varies from 6.8 to 7.0^8 which agrees fairly well with the values obtained for humic and hymatomelanic acids investigated in the present work excepting Chinsura humic acid which has got a high pK_{av} value (≈ 8.9).

The pK_{int} values of the acids were calculated as the intercepts at $\alpha = 0$ by plotting $\left(\text{pH} - \log \frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha} \right)$ against α^9 (Tanford, p. 551). Figs. 3(A) and 3(B) show the relevant

8. A. M. Pommer and I. A. Breger, *Geochim. Cosmoch. Acta.*, 1960, 20, 30-44.

9. C. Tanford, *Physical Chemistry of Macromolecules*, John Wiley and Sons, Inc., 1965.

graphs of humic acids* which are more or less linear over a considerable range of neutralisation. The pk_{int} values thus obtained are given in Table II. It has been observed that the curves in absence of electrolyte are not so linear as in its presence. The non-linearity of the curves indicates that 'w' in $\log \frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha} - pH = pk_{int} - 0.868 w n \alpha^9$ is not constant. All these acids are polyelectrolytes and in presence of an electrolyte the polyelectrolytic behaviour is suppressed *i.e.*, the molecules are coiled as a result of which the curve becomes linear, because 'w' is constant. The pk_{int} values are consequently lowered.

The lack of break at the first equivalence point may make it difficult to decide whether the acid is monoprotic or polyprotic. Recently Sturrock¹⁰ has suggested that if the change in pH, *i.e.*, ΔpH between the $\frac{1}{4}$ th and $\frac{3}{4}$ ths titration points is about 0.954, then the acid is said to be monoprotic and the experimental values of ΔpH may be employed as a simple, yet sensitive, criterion to determine whether an unknown acid is monoprotic. The values of pH at $\frac{1}{4}$ th and at $\frac{3}{4}$ ths titration points and the change in pH between them are given in Table III, indicating them to be polyprotic as the ΔpH values for these acids are

TABLE III

Acid	pH $\frac{1}{4}$	pH $\frac{3}{4}$	ΔpH	Conclusion
<i>Humic acid from</i>				
Palampur	5.95	8.40	2.45	polyprotic
Chinsura	7.70	9.20	1.50	„
Dehra Dun	6.50	8.75	2.25	„
Darjeeling	6.90	8.45	1.55	„
Jodhpur	5.52	8.95	2.43	„
<i>Hymatomelanic acid from</i>				
Palampur	6.20	8.30	2.10	polyprotic
Dehra Dun	6.12	8.75	2.63	„
Darjeeling	5.95	8.70	2.75	„

greater than 0.954. It may be noted that the polyprotic behaviour has also been similarly confirmed in the case of soil fulvic acids⁵.

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Received May 22, 1970

* The graphs of hymatomelanic acids having similar features are not included.

10. Peter E. Sturrock, *J. Chem. Ed.*, 1968, **45**, No. 4, 258.